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Research Article

Development And Validation Of RP-HPLC Methods For Estimation of Pregabalin and Pyridoxine Hydrochloride in Synthetic Mixture

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ABSTRACT

Pregabalin is a gamma-aminobutyric acid (GABA) analog that acts on the central nervous system. It is primarily used for the treatment of various neuropathic conditions. Pyridoxine Hydrochloride, also known as Vitamin B6. This study focuses on the development and validation of a reliable Reverse Phase High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (RP-HPLC) method for the simultaneous estimation of Pregabalin and Pyridoxine Hydrochloride in synthetic mixture. The validation of this method was achieved as per ICH Q2 (R2) guidelines with the optimized experimental conditions. To achieve the proposed method on Hypersil ODS C18, 250 mm*4.6 mm column as Stationary Phase and run time was 30 min. The Mobile Phase consists of 1% v/v orthophosphoric acid and acetonitrile in a ratio of 55:45%. UV detection was carried out at 250nm. The RP-HPLC method developed in this study ensures its accuracy, linearity, precision and reproducible analysis of both drugs.

INTRODUCTION

Pregabalin and Pyridoxine Hydrochloride are both pharmacologically significant agents used in the management of neurological conditions, especially those involving nerve damage or dysfunction. Their combination in a combination dosage form is designed to address the multifactorial nature of certain neurological

disorders, providing a comprehensive treatment approach. The development of an analytical method to estimate these drugs simultaneously is crucial for ensuring the safety, efficacy, and quality of such complex formulations.

Pregabalin:

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Pregabalin is a gamma-aminobutyric acid (GABA) analog that acts on the central nervous system. Pregabalin is an anti-convulsants drugs. It is primarily used for the treatment of various neuropathic conditions. Neuropathic pain, which results from nerve injury or damage, is one of the most common conditions treated with Pregabalin. The chemical name of Pregabalin is (S)-3-(aminomethyl)-5-methylhexanoic acid. It has a molecular formula of $C_8H_{17}NO_2$. Molecular weight 159.23 g/mol.

Fig 1: Structure of Pregabalin

Pyridoxine Hydrochloride (Vitamin B6):

Pyridoxine Hydrochloride is often used alongside other therapeutic agents to enhance nerve function and alleviate symptoms. It also acts as a cofactor in the synthesis of neurotransmitters like serotonin, dopamine, and gamma-aminobutyric acid (GABA), which are crucial for nerve health. The chemical name of Pyridoxine Hydrochloride is 4,5-bis(hydroxymethyl)-2-methylpyridin-3-ol;hydrochloride. It has a molecular formula of $C_8H_{11}NO_3$. Molecular weight 205.64 g/mol.

Fig 2: Structure of Pyridoxine Hydrochloride

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Table:1 Instrument specification for High Performance LC

Make	Cyberlab
Model	LC 100
Type	Binary Gradient
Detector	UV Detector
Software	LC Solution
Column	HYPERSIL ODS C18, 250 mm*4.6 mm
Pump	High Pressure Gradient (Reciprocating pump)

Table:2 Instrument specifications for weighing balance

Make	Mettler Toledo
Sensitivity	0.1 milligram
Minimum weighing capacity	1 milligram

Table:3 Instrument specification for melting point apparatus

Make	Gallenkamp
Design no.	889339

Table:4 Instrument Specification for UV double beam Spectrophotometer

Make	Shimadzu
Model	UV 1800
Type	Double beam spectrophotometer
Detector	Photodiode
Scanning Range	190-1100
Output	%T & Absorbance
Software	U.V. Probe 2.42

Table.5: Procurement of pure APIs

Sr.No.	Name of APIs	Source
1	Pregabalin Derivative Benzyl Chloride	Aarti Pharmalabs
2	Pyridoxine Hydrochloride	BASF

Identification of Drugs:**Solution Stability**

The solubility of Pregabalin & Pyridoxine Hydrochloride practically determined separately by taking 100 mg of both the drugs in 100 ml volumetric flasks, adding required quantity of solvent at room temperature and shaken for few minutes. Solubility data for each study was observed and recorded in Table 9.

Table.6: Solubility Table

Description Terms	Relative Quantities of solvent for 1 Parts of solute
Very soluble	Less than 1 part
Freely soluble	From 1 to 10 parts
Soluble	From 10 to 30 parts
Sparingly soluble	From 30 to 100 parts
Slightly soluble	From 300 to 1000 parts
Very slightly soluble	From 1000 to 10000 parts
Practically Insoluble	More than 10000 parts

Table.7: Solubility Data for Pregabalin Derivative Benzyl Chloride & Pyridoxine Hydrochloride

Solvent	Pregabalin	Pyridoxine Hydrochloride
Water	Slightly Soluble	Very Soluble
Chloroform	Freely Soluble	Practically Insoluble
0.1 N HCL	Slightly Soluble	Very slightly soluble
Acetonitrile	Freely Soluble	Sparingly Soluble
Methanol	Slightly Soluble	Soluble
Ethanol	Freely Soluble	Slightly Soluble

Identification by Melting Point Determination

Melting point of Pregabalin & Pyridoxine Hydrochloride hydrochloride has been determined. The melting points of the compounds were taken by open capillary method.

Table.8: Melting Point of Drugs

Sr. No.	APIs	Melting Point	
		Reported	Measured
1	Pregabalin	135.8 °C	135.6-139.8 °C
2	Pyridoxine Hydrochloride	207°C	207 °C

IR Spectra for Identification of drugs:**IR Spectra of pregabalin:**

Fig.3 IR Spectra of Pregabalin

Table.9: IR Interpretation of Pregabalin

Groups	General Range(cm-1)	Observed Range(cm-1)
N-H (s)	3400-3200	3319.39
C-O (s)	1650-1950	1744.55
C-H (s)	2690-2850	2928.47

C-N (s)	2240-2260	2245.55
C=O (s)	1640-1680	1660.77
C-C (s)	1200-900	1140.60

IR Spectra of Pyridoxine Hydrochloride:

Fig. 4 IR Spectra of Pyridoxine Hydrochloride

Table.10: IR Interpretation of Pyridoxine Hydrochloride

Groups	General Range(cm-1)	Observed Range(cm-1)
O-H (s)	3400-3200	3250.89
C=N (s)	1690-1640	1650.40
C=C (s)	1650-1550	1570.99

C-H (s)	1500-1300	1450.68
C-N(s)	1350-1250	1340.46
C-O(s)	1300-1000	1250.60
C-C(s)	1200-900	1150.80

Development and Optimization of HPLC Method:

Selection of Wavelength

To determine wavelength for measurement, standard spectra of Pregabalin Derivative Benzyl Chloride & Pyridoxine Hydrochloride were scanned between 200-400 nm against diluents. Absorbance maxima of Pregabalin Derivative

Benzyl Chloride & Pyridoxine Hydrochloride detected at 240 nm & 263 nm. Chromatogram was taken at 250 nm, both drugs give good peak height and shape. So, 250nm was selected for Simultaneous estimation of Pregabalin Derivative Benzyl Chloride & Pyridoxine Hydrochloride their formulation. The UV overlain spectrum for Pregabalin & Pyridoxine Hydrochloride shown in fig No.5.

Fig.5 UV Spectra of Pregabalin derivative Benzyl Chloride Pyridoxine Hydrochloride

Selection of Chromatographic Conditions

Proper selection of the HPLC method depends upon the nature of the sample (ionic or ionisable or neutral molecule), its molecular weight, pKa and solubility. HPLC was selected for the initial separation based on literature survey and its simplicity and suitability. To optimize the chromatographic conditions the effect of chromatographic variables such as mobile phase, flow rate and solvent ratio were studied. Finally, the chromatographic condition was chosen that give the best resolution, symmetry and capacity factor for estimation of both drugs.

Selection of Column

For HPLC Method, various columns are available but based on literature survey C-18 (id 4.6 x 150 mm, 5 μ m) was selected over the other columns.

Preparation of Solution

Preparation of Mobile Phase

HPLC method was followed by isocratic elution technique. Mobile phase comprised of 1% v/v orthophosphoric acid and acetonitrile in a ratio of 55:45% v/v. pH Adjustment to 3.0 using triethylamine as it elutes both drugs peak efficiently in short time with satisfactory resolution, tailing factor and theoretical plates. The mobile phase is ideal for promoting good separation and accurate quantification of the

analytes in a controlled and reproducible manner. The acidic nature of the orthophosphoric acid helps with the ionization of the compounds, while the acetonitrile provides the necessary polarity to enhance resolution and shorten analysis times.

Preparation of Standard Stock Solution A: (Pregabalin Stock Solution)

Accurately weighed quantity of 100 mg of Pregabalin in 1ml of (DCM). Add 0.1ml of Benzyl Chloride to pregabalin solution. Add 0.1ml of 1M NaOH. Transferred into 100 mL volumetric flask, dissolved in methanol and diluted up to mark with methanol. This will give a stock solution having strength of 1000 µg/mL. Withdraw 7.5 ml from Stock Solution and make up to 10 ml to get 750 µg/mL.

Preparation of Standard Stock Solution B: (Pyridoxine Hydrochloride stock solution)

Accurately weighed quantity of Pyridoxine Hydrochloride 10 mg was transferred into 100 mL volumetric flask, dissolved in methanol and diluted up to mark with methanol. This will give a stock solution having strength of 100 µg/mL. Withdraw 1.5 ml from Stock Solution and make up to 10 ml with to get 15 µg/mL.

Chromatographic condition

The chromatographic separation of Pregabalin and Pyridoxine Hydrochloride were achieved on C-18 (id 4.6 x 150 mm, 5 µm) by using mobile phase composed of 1% v/v orthophosphoric acid and acetonitrile in a ratio of 55:45% v/v, at flow rate 1.0 ml/min with run time of 30 minutes. Detection of both drugs was carried out at 254 nm by using diluent as mobile phase.

Method of validation

As per ICH guideline (Q2R1), the method validation parameters studied were specificity, linearity, accuracy, precision, limit of detection, limit of quantitation and robustness.

Specificity

The analytical method for specificity was evaluated by injecting the following solutions. Diluent was prepared and inject into the HPLC system in triplicate. Sample solution was prepared with appropriate levels of excipients as a placebo sample and inject into the HPLC system in triplicate for all the dosage strengths. Placebo was prepared by mixing all excipients without active ingredients. Standard and sample solutions were prepared for assay (100% Conc.) and inject into the HPLC system in triplicate.

Linearity and Range

Preparation of Solution for linearity studies: For the purpose of linearity, accurately weighed amount of Pregabalin Derivative Benzyl Chloride (75 mg), and Pyridoxine Hydrochloride (1.5 mg) was taken into the volumetric flask (10 ml) and volume of the flask was raised to 10 ml with methyl alcohol to give stock solution containing 750µg/ml of Pregabalin, and 15 µg/ml of Pyridoxine Hydrochloride. Various aliquots from this stock solution were transferred to another 10 ml volumetric flask and volume was raised to the mark with mobile phase to give final solutions containing 50+1, 75+1.5, 100+2, 125+2.5 and 150+3µg/ml of Pregabalin and Pyridoxine Hydrochloride respectively.

Precision

Repeatability

Prepared standard working solution of mixtures having concentration of Pregabalin Derivative Benzyl Chloride (750 µg/ml) and Pyridoxine

Hydrochloride (15 µg/ml) were injected at volume of 20 µL into column by employing optimized chromatographic conditions. Each standard mixture was injected 5 time and peak area was monitored. Each concentration was monitored for repeatability by RSD.

Intra-day and Inter-day Precision

- Method precision was determined by performing intraday and inter day precision.
- Mixture that represents overall range (Pregabalin Derivative Benzyl Chloride +Pyridoxine Hydrochloride = 50+1, 100+2 and 150+3 µg/ml) were analyzed on same day at different time interval for intraday precision.
- Mixture that represents overall range (Pregabalin Derivative Benzyl Chloride +Pyridoxine Hydrochloride = 50+1, 100+2 and 150+3 µg/ml)were analyzed on different days for inter-day precision.

System Suitability Parameters

Solution of Pregabalin + Pyridoxine Hydrochloride (100+100 µg.ml⁻¹) was injected 3 times for determination of System suitability parameters which includes Retention time (Rt), Tailing factor (Tf), Resolution (Rs) and number of theoretical plates. System suitability parameters for selected concentration were determined by C.V.

Accuracy

Accuracy of the analytical method has been performed by spiking of sample with the standard. Spiking of the placebo was performed at 50,100 and 150 % of the target concentration

Limit of detection and Limit of Quantification

The limit of detection (LOD) and the limit of quantification (LOQ) were calculated using the standard deviation of y-intercept of calibration curve. The limit of detection (LOD) and the limit of quantification (LOQ):

$$LOQ = 10 \sigma/s \text{ and } LOD = 3.3 \sigma/s$$

Where, σ = the standard deviation of the response.

S = the slope of the calibration curve

Robustness

Following parameters were altered one by one for determination of robustness of the method and their effect was observed by comparing with the standard preparation. Mobile phase flowrate (± 0.1 mL/min), optimized flowrate was 1.0 mL/min. Mobile phase composition (± 2 mL), in optimized ratio 2 determinations of Pregabalin Derivative Benzyl Chloride + Pyridoxine Hydrochloride for each alteration were carried out and RSD was measured.

Assay

Sample preparation	
Label claim: Mix pregabalin 750 mg + Pyridoxine HCL 15 mg, dissolve it in 50 ml of methanol and sonicate it for 15 min. Heat at 30 °C until base is dissolved and cool it at room temperature. Filter the extract through whatmann filter paper no. 42 and make up the volume up to 100 ml with methanol. Take 1 ml of dilute to 10 ml, Final stock solution containing PGB(750 µg/ml) + PYRI HCL (15 µg/ml).	
Test solution:	Withdraw 100µl from above filtrate in 10 mL volumetric flask; make up the volume with mobile phase, which contain Pregabalin Derivative Benzyl Chloride +Pyridoxine Hydrochloride = 75+1.5 µg/ml. Inject the above solution for 3 times under optimized.

Procedure of for derivatization of Pregabalin

Structure of Pregabalin and its suitability for derivatization.

Pregabalin chemically (S)-3-(aminomethyl)-5-methylhexanoic acid. The molecule is highly saturated, aliphatic chain with single bonds except for C=O bond. Such bonding chemistry of Pregabalin, makes it poor candidate for UV light absorption and hence making it almost ineligible for analysis by techniques which explore phenomenon UV radiation such as HPLC-UV or UV-Spectrophotometry. Although presence of COOH group makes its estimation pretty easy by titration from bulk API lots but is unsuitable for analysis pregabalin in the dosage forms which contain interfering excipients. The structure as shown in the Figure-1, has two functional groups, carboxylic acid (COOH) and primary amine (NH₂), both groups amenable for derivitization. The derivitization of drugs for the purpose of analysis, needs to be simple, cost effective, safe and environment friendly. Most importantly, the dervitizing reactions essentially be short, single step and can be carried out at general laboratory conditions. The presence of both primary amine and carboxylic acid groups in the structure makes

molecule more explicable for modification into UV into absorbing species, however considering structural constrains, it appears that exploring amine groups appears to less complicated.

Benzoylation of Pregabalin

The benzoylation generally reaction of primary amine with or OH group with benzoyl chloride resulting in the formation of an amide or ester. The benzoylation of phenolic OH requires drastic conditions of 0 high temperatures of 125-175 C with addition of benzoyl chloride. On other hand, benzoylation at primary amine was reported to be relatively less complex. Benzoylation of amines involves, reaction acyl chloride with an amine so that an amide is formed, together with a proton and a chloride ion. Addition of a base is required to neutralize this acidic proton, otherwise the reaction will not proceed. Generally the aqueous solution of a base is slowly added to the reaction mixture to neutralize incoming proton. For zwitterion molecules such as amino acids, base also keeps COOH group ionized and prevents amine group being protonated. General scheme for benzoylation of amines is given below.

Fig 6: Benzoylation of Pregabalin

RESULT AND DISCUSSION:

Selection of Wavelength

To determine wavelength for measurement, standard spectra of Pregabalin Derivative Benzyl

Chloride & Pyridoxine Hydrochloride were scanned between 200-400 nm against diluents. Absorbance maxima of Pregabalin Derivative Benzyl Chloride & Pyridoxine Hydrochloride detected at 240 nm & 263 nm. Chromatogram was taken at 250 nm, both drugs give good peak height and shape. So, 250nm was selected for Simultaneous estimation of Pregabalin Derivative Benzyl Chloride & Pyridoxine Hydrochloride their formulation. The UV overlain spectrum for Pregabalin & Pyridoxine Hydrochloride in their formulation.

Selection of Mobile phase

Trail 1

Column: C-18 (id 4.6 x 250 mm, 5 μ m)

Mobile Phase: Acetonitrile:Water(30:9.0v/v)

Detection: 250 nm

Flow rate:1 ml/min

Run Time: 10 minutes

Observations: No peak detected.

Fig.7 Trial 1: Chromatogram of PGB + Pyri HCL Acetonitrile: Water(30:9.0v/v)

Trail 2

Column: C-18 (id 4.6 x 250 mm, 5 μ m)

Mobile Phase: Acetonitrile:Water(50:50v/v)

Detection: 250 nm

Flow rate:1 ml/min

Run Time: 10 minutes

Observations: Only one Peak detected but broad peaks observe.

Fig.8 Trial 2: Chromatogram of PGB + Pyri HCL Acetonitrile: Water (50:50v/v)

Trail 3

Flow rate: 1 ml/min

Column: C-18 (id 4.6 x 250 mm, 5 μ m)

Run Time: 10 minutes

Mobile Phase: Acetonitrile:Water (80:20v/v)

Observations: Only one Peak detected but broad peaks observe.

Detection: 250 nm

Fig.9 Trial 3: Chromatogram of PGB + Pyri HCL Acetonitrile: Water (80:20v/v)

Trail 4

Detection: 250 nm

Column: C-18 (id 4.6 x 250 mm, 5 μ m)

Flow rate: 1 ml/min

Mobile Phase: Ethanol: Phosphate Buffer (60:40v/v)

Run Time: 10minutes

Observations: only one peak detected.

Fig.10 Trial 4: Chromatogram of PGB + Pyri HCL Ethanol: Phosphate Buffer (60:40v/v)

Trail 5

Detection: 250 nm

Column: C-18 (id 4.6 x 250 mm, 5 μ m)

Flow rate: 1 ml/min

Mobile Phase: Chloroform: Acetonitrile (9.0:30v/v)

Run Time: 10minutes

Observations: only one peak detected.

Fig.11 Trial 5: Chromatogram of PGB + Pyri HCL Chloroform: Acetonitrile (9.0:30v/v)

Trail 6

Detection: 250 nm

Column: C-18 (id 4.6 x 250 mm, 5 μ m)

Flow rate: 1 ml/min

Mobile Phase: Chloroform: Acetonitrile (50:50v/v)

Run Time: 10minutes

Observations: Peaks detected and separated, but broad peaks observe.

Fig.12 Trial 6: Chromatogram of PGB + Pyri HCL Chloroform: Acetonitrile (50:50v/v)

Trail 7

Detection: 250 nm

Column: C-18 (id 4.6 x 150 mm, 5 μ m)

Flow rate: 1 ml/min

Mobile Phase: 1% v/v orthophosphoric acid and acetonitrile in a ratio of (30:70v/v)

Run Time: 30 minutes

Observations: No peak detected.

Fig.13 Trial 1: Chromatogram of PGB + Pyri HCL with 1% v/v OPA acid and ACN in a ratio of 30:70v/v)

Trail 8

Detection: 250 nm

Column: C-18 (id 4.6 x 150 mm, 5 μ m)

Flow rate: 1 ml/min

Mobile Phase: 1% v/v orthophosphoric acid and acetonitrile in a ratio of (50:50v/v)

Run Time: 30minutes

Observations: only one peak detected.

Fig.14 Trial 2: Chromatogram of PGB + Pyri HCL with 1% v/v OPA acid and ACN in a ratio of (50:50v/v)

Trial 9

Flow rate: 1 ml/min

Column: C-18 (id 4.6 x 150 mm, 5 μ m)

Run Time: 30minutes

Mobile Phase: 1% v/v orthophosphoric acid and acetonitrile in a ratio of (20:80v/v)

Observations: Peaks detected and separated, but broad peaks observe.

Detection: 250 nm

Fig.15 Trial 3: Chromatogram of PGB + Pyri HCL with 1% v/v OPA acid and ACN in a ratio of (20:80v/v)

Trial 10

Mobile Phase: 1% v/v orthophosphoric acid and acetonitrile in a ratio of 55:45%

Column: C-18 (id 4.6 x 150 mm, 5 μ m)

Detection: 250 nm

Stationary phase: C-18 (id 4.6 x 150 mm, 5 μ m)

Flow rate: 1 ml/min

Mobile Phase: 1% v/v orthophosphoric acid and acetonitrile in a ratio of 55:45%

Run Time: 30 minutes

Detection: 250 nm

Observations: Good peaks with Adequate solution was observed.

Flow rate: 1 ml/min

Run Time: 30 minutes

Fig.16 Trial 4: Chromatogram of PGB + Pyri HCL with 1% v/v OPA acid and ACN in a ratio of (55:45v/v)

Detector: UV detector

Injection volume: 20 μ l

7.5.3 Chromatographic conditions for optimized mobile phase trial

Column Temperature: 40°C

Mode: Isocratic

Fig.17: Optimized mobile phase trial for optimized chromatogram of Std. Pregabalin Derivative Benzyl Chloride:10.221 min, Pyridoxine Hydrochloride: 13.115 min

Fig.18: Chromatogram of blank 1% v/v orthophosphoric acid and acetonitrile in a ratio of (55:45%v/v)

Fig.19: Chromatogram of Pregabalin with 1% v/v orthophosphoric acid and acetonitrile in a ratio of (55:45%v/v)

Fig.20: Chromatogram of Pyridoxine hydrochloride with 1% v/v orthophosphoric acid and acetonitrile in a ratio of (55:45%v/v)

Method Validation

Linearity

For the purpose of linearity, accurately weighed amount of Pregabalin Derivative Benzyl Chloride (10 mg), and Pyridoxine Hydrochloride (10 mg) was taken into the volumetric flask (10 ml) and volume of the flask was raised to 10 ml with

methyl alcohol to give stock solution containing 100 µg/ml of Pregabalin, and 100 µg/ml of Pyridoxine Hydrochloride. Various aliquots from this stock solution were transferred to another 10 ml volumetric flask and volume was raised to the mark with mobile phase to give final solutions containing 50+1, 75+1.5, 100+2, 125+2.5 and 150+3 µg/ml of Pregabalin and Pyridoxine Hydrochloride respectively.

Table.11: Linearity data for Pregabalin Derivative Benzyl Chloride and Pyridoxine Hydrochloride

Pregabalin Derivative Benzyl Chloride			
Conc. (µg/ml)	Mean Area	± SD (n=5)	% RSD
50.0	102791	102791 ± 149.01	0.14
75.0	164800	164800 ± 306.25	0.19
100.0	205650	205650 ± 1086.79	0.53
125.0	257038	257038 ± 1749.10	0.71
150.0	305352	305352 ± 1083.92	0.35

Pyridoxine Hydrochloride			
Conc. (µg/ml)	Mean Area	± SD (n=5)	% RSD
1.0	191227	191227 ± 702.78	0.37
1.5	302183	302183 ± 281.72	0.09

2.0	385651	385651 ± 851.10	0.22
2.5	470850	470850 ± 57.49	0.01
3.0	578430	578430 ± 827.17	0.14

Fig.21: Overlain Linearity Spectra of Pregabalin Derivative Benzyl Chloride and Pyridoxine Hydrochloride

Fig.22: Calibration curve of Pregabalin Derivative Benzyl Chloride

Fig.23: Calibration curve of Pyridoxine Hydrochloride

Table.12: Linearity results for Pregabalin Derivative Benzyl Chloride and Pyridoxine Hydrochloride

Regression Analysis	Pregabalin Derivative Benzyl Chloride	Pyridoxine Hydrochloride
Concentration Range	50-150 µg/mL	1-3 µg/mL
Regression equation	$y = 2003x + 5533.3$	$y = 195860x - 5986.9$
Correlation coefficient	0.9967	0.9999

Precision

Repeatability

The data for repeatability for Pregabalin Derivative Benzyl Chloride and Pyridoxine Hydrochloride is shown in table 13. The % R.S.D For Repeatability data was found to be 0.48 % for Pregabalin derivative benzyl chloride and 0.49 % for Pyridoxine hydrochloride.

Table.13: Repeatability data for Pregabalin and Pyridoxine Hydrochloride

Drugs	Conc. (µg/ml)	Mean Peak Area ± SD	%RSD
Pregabalin Derivative Benzyl Chloride	75	441124.11 ± 2120.15	0.48
Pyridoxine Hydrochloride	1.5	654279.14 ± 3188.52	0.49

Inter-day precision

The data for interday precision for Pregabalin Derivative Benzyl Chloride and Pyridoxine Hydrochloride is shown in table 14. The % R.S.D for intraday precision was found to be 0.19-0.58 % for Pregabalin and 0.10-0.43 % for Pyridoxine Hydrochloride.

Table.14: Inter-day precision data for estimation of Pregabalin Derivative Benzyl Chloride and Pyridoxine Hydrochloride

Mcg/ml	Pregabalin Derivative Benzyl Chloride			Pyridoxine Hydrochloride		
	75%	100 %	125 %	75%	100 %	125 %
	1044 92	2094 65	3148 96	1955 68	3885 09	5829 64
	1051 52	2081 55	3137 41	1938 87	3868 51	5826 41
	1052 58	2070 51	3139 85	1945 89	3867 82	5818 54
MEA N	1049 67	2082 24	3142 07	1946 81	3873 81	5824 86
± SD	415. 048	1207 .46	607. 75	844. 29	977. 77	570. 93
RSD	0.40	0.58	0.19	0.43	0.25	0.10

Table.16: Recovery data for Pregabalin Derivative Benzyl Chloride

	Pregabalin					
	50%		100%		150%	
	Amount of drug recovered (mg)	%Recovery	Amount of drug recovered (mg)	%Recovery	Amount of drug recovered (mg)	%Recovery
	1.46	99.76	2.97	99.20	4.54	100.20

Intra-day precision

The data for intra-day precision for Pregabalin Derivative Benzyl Chloride and Pyridoxine Hydrochloride is shown in table 15. The % R.S.D for intraday precision was found to be 0.06-0.13 % for Pregabalin and 0.09 -0.17 % for Pyridoxine Hydrochloride.

Table.15: Intra-day precision data for estimation of Pregabalin Derivative Benzyl Chloride and Pyridoxine Hydrochloride

Mcg/ml	Pregabalin Derivative Benzyl Chloride			Pyridoxine Hydrochloride		
	75%	100 %	125 %	75%	100 %	125 %
	1065 86	2082 56	3139 65	1954 78	3888 74	5842 54
	1052 47	2084 97	3136 54	1958 69	3899 68	5835 67
	1053 68	2087 85	3135 96	1956 72	3887 45	5845 86
MEA N	1057 34	2085 13	3137 38	1956 73	3891 96	5841 36
± SD	740. 61	264. 84	197. 42	196. 50	671. 96	519. 70
RSD	0.70	0.13	0.06	0.10	0.17	0.09

Accuracy

Accuracy of the method was confirmed by recovery study from synthetic mixture at three level standard additions. Percentage recovery for Pregabalin Derivative Benzyl Chloride & Pyridoxine Hydrochloride was found to be 99.48-99.78% and 99.33-100.59 % respectively. The results are shown in table.16-17.

	1.40	97.70	2.89	99.01	4.56	100.22
	1.56	100.50	3.09	100.01	4.68	100.30
Mean	1.49	96.65	2.98	99.43	4.69	100.24
%RSD	0.02	1.30	0.04	1.75	0.05	0.68

Table.17: Recovery data for Pyridoxine Hydrochloride

	Pyridoxine Hydrochloride					
	50%		100%		150%	
	Amount of drug recovered (mg)	%Recovery	Amount of drug recovered (mg)	%Recovery	Amount of drug recovered (mg)	%Recovery
	1.48	99.70	2.96	99.19	4.52	100.17
	1.42	97.89	3.05	99.80	4.57	100.28
	1.52	100.55	3.01	100.02	4.54	99.80
Mean	1.47	96.65	3.01	99.67	4.54	100.08
%RSD	0.01	1.30	0.06	1.80	0.03	0.63

LOD and LOQ

The limit of detection (LOD) and Limit of Quantification (LOQ) was found to be as per below:

Table.18: LOD and LOQ Limit for Pregabalin Derivative Benzyl Chloride & Pyridoxine Hydrochloride

Pregabalin Derivative Benzyl Chloride		Pyridoxine Hydrochloride	
LOD($\mu\text{g}/\text{m l}$)	LOQ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m l}$)	LOD($\mu\text{g}/\text{m l}$)	LOQ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m l}$)
0.80	1.50	0.75	1.80

Selectivity

There is no interference in the mixture.

Robustness

The method is found to be robust as the results were not significantly affected by slight variation in Mobile Phase Composition and flow rate of mobile phase. The results are shown in table 19. Variation seen was within the acceptable range respect to peak asymmetry and theoretical plates, so the method was found to be robust.

Table.19: Robustness data for Pregabalin Derivative Benzyl Chloride & Pyridoxine Hydrochloride

Parameter	Level of Change	Effect on assay volume			
		Pregabalin Derivative Benzyl Chloride Pyridoxine Hydrochloride			
		Assay \pm SD	RSD	Assay \pm SD	RSD
Flow rate	0.9 mL/min	97.70 \pm 0.50	0.49	97.92 \pm 0.48	0.48
	1.1 mL/min	101.09 \pm 0.72	0.72	97.99 \pm 0.83	0.83
Mobile phase composition	55:45	97.47 \pm 0.53	0.53	100.22 \pm 1.43	1.43
	53:47	97.39 \pm 0.99	0.98	100.04 \pm 1.06	1.06
	57:43	99.51 \pm 0.67	0.67	99.45 \pm 0.77	0.78

Analysis of marketed product

The proposed method was successfully applied to analysis of the commercially available tablet

formulation. The % drugs were found satisfactory, which is comparable with the corresponding label claim.

Table.20: Analysis of marketed formulations

Drug	Amount taken ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Amount found ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	% Assy
Pregabalin Derivative Benzyl Chloride	3	2.93 \pm 0.04	99.80 \pm 1.20
Pyridoxine Hydrochloride	3	3.03 \pm 0.10	100.70 \pm 1.07

Summary Of Method Validation:**Table.21: Summary of validation parameter of RP-HPLC method**

Optimized chromatographic Condition	
Stationary Phase	C-18 (id 4.6 x 150 mm, 5 μm)
Mobile Phase	1% v/v orthophosphoric acid and acetonitrile in a ratio of 55:45%

Detection wave Length	250 nm
Flow rate	1 ml/minute
Run time	30 minutes
Retention Time	Pregabalin Derivative Benzyl Chloride: 10.225 min, Pyridoxine Hydrochloride: 13.115 min.

Validation Parameters				
Parameter	Limit	Result		Conclusion
		Pregabalin Derivative Benzyl Chloride	Pyridoxine Hydrochloride	
Linearity and Range	R ² > 0.995	0.9967 (50-150 $\mu\text{g/mL}$)	0.9998 (1-3 $\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Method was linear
Repeatability	RSD<2	0.09-0.64	0.10-0.87	Method was repeatable
LOD	-	0.80	1.50	-
LOQ	-	0.75	1.80	-
Intra-day Precision	RSD<2	0.19-0.58	0.10-0.43	Method was precise
Inter-Day Precision	RSD<2	0.06-0.13	0.09-0.17	Method was precise
%Recovery	98-102%	99.35 \pm 0.83–100.01 \pm 0.03 %	100.22 \pm 0.21 – 100.78 \pm 0.23%	Method was accurate
Robustness	RSD<2	0.41– 0.63	0.40-0.91	Method was robust
Assay%		99.80 \pm 1.20	100.70 \pm 1.07	-

CONCLUSION:

A method for the development and validation of a High-Performance Liquid Chromatography

(HPLC) technique for the simultaneous determination of Pregabalin derivative, Benzyl Chloride, and Pyridoxine Hydrochloride has been successfully established. Mobile phase for

Pregabalin derivative, Benzyl Chloride, and Pyridoxine Hydrochloride 1% v/v orthophosphoric acid and acetonitrile in a ratio of 55:45% v/v. pH Adjustment: pH adjusted to 3.0 using trimethylamine taken. 250 nm wavelength taken for Pregabalin derivative, Benzyl Chloride, and Pyridoxine Hydrochloride. In conclusion, the developed and validated HPLC method is a promising, efficient, and reliable approach for the determination of Pregabalin derivative, Benzyl Chloride, and Pyridoxine Hydrochloride in pharmaceutical products, contributing to better quality control practices and patient safety.

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